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Determination of the Duration of single Pregnancy in Dakar and the Contributing Factors

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Abstract

Objectives: To determine the duration of single-fetal pregnancy in black Senegalese women and the factors that contribute to it.

Patients and methods: This is a retrospective and prospective cross-sectional study that evaluated parturients admitted to the Philippe Maguilen Senghor health center for the management of their delivery of a monofoetal pregnancy from January 1, 2012 to December 31, 2018. All parturients with the following characteristics were included: monofoetal pregnancy, date of last menstrual period known or reconstituted on the basis of an early ultrasound ($\leq 13SA + 6$ days), a term of pregnancy greater than or equal to 37 weeks, spontaneous induction from work and a child living at birth. The data was entered into our e-Perinatal computer database and analyzed first on Microsoft Excel 2016 and then using SPSS 24 Mac version software. The continuous quantitative variables were described by their position and dispersion parameters: mean, median, mode and standard deviation. They were compared using the ANOVA test. The relationship between the quantitative variables was assessed using a bivariate linear correlation. The level of significance used was 0.05.

Results: Over 7 years, 13,292 parturients met the inclusion criteria, representing a frequency of 35.6% of all admissions. The average age was 27.36 years with extremes of 13 and 49 years. Almost 9 in 10 parturients were under the age of 35. The average duration of gestation was 278.69 days, the median was 278 days while the mode was 279 days; which corresponded respectively to 39SA + 6 days, 39SA + 5 days and 39SA + 6 days. Parity, maternal age and type of fetal presentation did not influence the duration of pregnancy. However, male fetuses were born on average one day earlier (39SA + 5) compared to female fetuses.

Conclusion: The Senegalese black woman gives birth on average 6 to 10 days earlier than the Caucasian woman. Boys are born a day earlier than girls. It is necessary to encourage women to remember the date of their last period and to consult early enough for an early ultrasound. Finally, it is necessary to consider a larger study to clarify the duration of pregnancy in black women on an African scale in order to provide recommendations for clinical practice.

Keywords: Duration of pregnancy; Expected date of delivery; Dakar

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